

INTEGRATED AUTOMATED BANKING SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *The most effective way to ensure the competitiveness of banks is the automation of banking systems. Digital banking technologies and their content and elements are widely covered in the article. The scientific views of foreign and domestic scientists on banking technologies were studied, analyzed and author's opinions were expressed. In addition, the role and importance of automated banking systems for the effective use of banking technologies and their further improvement is highlighted.*

Key words: *banking technologies, information technologies, mobile banking, risk, computer, card, Internet banking, Play Market, ABS.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, every day is filled with news that is an important factor in the development of our country's economy, including new modern information and communication technologies in the banking sector, which is considered one of the important branches of the economy as a result of the rapid development of the world banking and financial system (There is an even greater need to use ICT.

In fact, speed, quality and transparency of all services provided by commercial banks using information technologies are today's requirements. It's no secret that various forms of modern remote banking services, which are now completely replacing traditional banking services, provide exactly this speed, quality and reliability. Modern banking services serve to increase the possibilities of customers by creating greater convenience.

As the first head of our state, Islam Karimov, stated in his speech at the extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers, dedicated to the results of socio-

economic development of our country in 2015 and the most important directions of the economic program for 2016, - "In today's conditions, the Internet and electronics During this period, the wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in economic sectors and the further development of the "Electronic Government" system are of priority importance. World experience shows that the role and importance of information and communication technologies, which includes computer and telecommunication technologies, production of software products and the provision of a wide range of interactive services based on them, is increasing in the global economy. Consistent and targeted reforms are being carried out in the banking system of Uzbekistan, a number of measures and decisions have been taken to fundamentally improve the quality of banking and financial services.

In this regard, in order to establish a modern and efficient system of settlements between individuals and parties receiving payments in the implementation of cashless retail payments in our republic, "Account clearing system of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan" "On" was developed and approved by the decision of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4/4 dated February 21, 2014, it was registered in the Ministry of Justice on April 4, 2014 with No. 2570 .

As a result of the ongoing reforms, market mechanisms for providing services are being introduced in the banking system, their types are expanding, and financial openness for entrepreneurs and residents is increasing.

New banking services have been introduced to facilitate the implementation of currency exchange operations for the population, opportunities have been created for the purchase of foreign currency by individual entrepreneurs.

At the same time, a number of problems and shortcomings are observed in the observance of the rights and legal interests of consumers of banking services, especially in the regions, and in the expansion of financial openness, as well as in further increasing the service culture and trust in the banking system. In particular:

1. The Association of Banks of Uzbekistan should be recommended to develop and implement a program of measures aimed at increasing the popularity of banking services and strengthening its role in improving banking activities, including the following:

- Approving the Concept of further increasing the efficiency of the Association of Banks of Uzbekistan;

- to improve the professional skills of banking system employees, to establish an exchange of experience with foreign banks based on advanced international experience;

- implementation of measures to increase the financial literacy of the population with the involvement of foreign experts together with the local state authorities;

- current problems of the popularity of banking services, study international experience and develop proposals for its application in the market of banking services of the republic, conduct research on the topic in connection with the organization of information-analytical and consulting services for banks and their clients;

- promoting initiatives to implement modern and advanced banking services in practice for the development of remote banking services, introducing new information technologies;

- to study the activities of advanced foreign banks in order to identify new types and products of banking services and their subsequent implementation in republican banks.

2. The Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan together with the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other interested agencies until January 1, 2019:

- funds calculated for citizens in the accumulated pension system;

- Calculated insurance contributions of citizens to the off-budget Pension Fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- calculated debts for taxes and other mandatory payments;

individuals and business entities for identification;

-property and other income of individuals;

Creation of a unified inter-departmental information system for data processing and electronic exchange between state bodies and credit bureaus, which allows obtaining information on the financial status of legal entities.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The most effective way to ensure the competitiveness of commercial banks is to gain the trust of customers and create all the conveniences for them, as well as to increase the type, quality and speed of services. In order to ensure competitiveness, banks feel a greater need to introduce modern banking services and use new technologies.

In particular, in this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev said in his speech "... this year we must take drastic measures to develop the banking system.

From 2020, a large-scale transformation program will be implemented in each bank. In this regard, increasing the capital, resource base and income of our banks will be in the center of our special attention" [1].

Taking into account the above, a number of documents were adopted in recent years, which envisage the liberalization of the banking system and adaptation to the conditions of free competition. In particular, the adoption of Resolution No. 3620 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 23, 2018 "On additional measures to increase the popularity of banking services", existing problems in the provision of banking services and implementation by banks determined the necessary measures [2].

In particular, the development and promotion of innovative products for non-cash payments, including non-contact and mobile technologies; introduction of non-communication and mobile technologies, first of all, in the spheres of social and household services, transport, trade, catering, especially in the regions; ensuring interoperability with international payment systems, etc.

Research works of a number of scientists on the topic were closely familiarized. In them, the opinions of scientists on remote banking services were analyzed. In particular, according to Russian economist V.K.Spilnichenko, "Remote servicing of a bank account is a complex of information services and execution of transactions on the client's account based on his instructions without visiting the bank. The remote bank account service system is based on the client's request to the bank's database through the telecommunication system [4].

And N.I. Likhodeyeva recognized the system of remote service to the bank account as a technology of providing banking services on the basis of remote orders without visiting the bank by the client using computer technologies [5].

K.A.Zabrodiskaya, A.O.Zakharova "Remote banking services are the activity of creating optimal conditions for the bank's customers by providing remote service to the bank account" [6].

Summarizing the above opinions, remote bank account servicing systems can be defined as technologies for providing banking services based on customer orders from a distance (without coming to the bank).

In recent years, banks have been offering various innovative banking services to improve the quality of services provided to customers. In particular, the traditional "Bank-client" system, which provides remote banking services, is widespread in our republic and is implemented in all banks. To use this system, a special program is installed on the client's computer, and interaction with the bank's information system is ensured through communication channels. However, due to the need to connect to a specific workplace and use specialized programs when using the "Bank-client" system, the possibility of using this system is limited. Therefore, the online banking (internetbanking) system is widely used, which provides operation through the Internet network and a simple browser, that is, a common program that allows the client to access the network.

Internet banking technology creates additional convenience for both the bank and customers. In particular, the client has the opportunity to carry out banking operations on his account from anywhere and at any time via the Internet

without going to the bank. can get information about actions. This creates the advantages of saving time and money for the client, freely choosing a bank regardless of the distance and proximity of the address, and quickly managing their funds.

Also, in cooperation with commercial banks that are participants of the "Uzcard" interbank payment system, the creation of a national technological platform that works in the "on-line" mode will allow the client to manage his card accounts in real time through Internet banking services, utility and other gives him the opportunity to fulfill his wishes.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

What are Automated Banking Systems (ABS)? This concept is closely related to the concept of automated information systems, which, in turn, have a dual nature: these information systems are information storage and processing systems that use modern technical tools necessary to perform technological operations. automated systems that are lum systems.

A system is something that has integrity. The system consists of their interrelated elements, which are ordered and combined with a goal unit. A system is a certain mechanism in which each of the components has its place and performs certain functions.

When formulating requirements for automated systems, the needs of the bank should be taken into account. Despite the differences and individuality of automated banking systems, they must all meet certain requirements.

The main requirements for modern automated bank systems can be divided into four parts:

1. basic requirements;
2. system engineering requirements (as a software tool);
3. special requirements (reflects the specific characteristics of banking activity);
4. quality indicators (describes the process of development of automated banking systems).

The general requirements of automated banking systems include functional completeness, information integration, openness, reliability of information, reliability, complexity, scale, various modes of operation, unified information space, consolidation, availability of an advanced work flow system.

Considering that the system users will not be experts in the field of information technologies, the first requirement is to protect the information from wrong actions of the operator. Data stored in bank systems is real money for the bank, so the bank's electronic system must be qualitatively protected from breaches and the actions of attackers.

One of the conceptual approaches to the creation of automated banking systems involves dividing the system's functionality into three levels. The upper level, "front-office", organizes modules that ensure fast and convenient data entry, its initial processing and interaction of the bank with clients, other banks, the Central Bank, etc. That is, it is a subsystem that ensures the bank's interaction with the outside world. Middle-level "back-office" is programs for various areas of activity within the bank and internal calculations. This is work with loans, deposits, securities, plastic cards. This subsystem provides general banking and general business operations. The lower level, "accounting", is the basic functions of accounting, or the core of accounting. It is here that the modules that ensure accounting, that is, the timely and correct reflection of the bank's activities, are the existing accounting procedures.

In our country, all banks are constantly taking measures to develop remote banking services. As a result of these measures, as of January 1, 2020, the total number of users of the service is 10 million. increased from (Table 1).

Distribution of the number of users of remote banking services among banks as of January 1, 2020 [7]

Table 1

No	Bank	Legal persons	Physical persons	Total
1	TIF National bank	52 969	1 657 243	1 710 212

2	"Uzbekistan industrial construction bank" ATB	31 464	777 366	808 830
3	"Agrobank" ATB	96 250	1 343 740	1 439 990
4	"Mortgage Bank" ATIB	98 400	870 055	968 455
5	"Microkreditbank" ATB	48 152	639 018	687 170
6	AT People's Bank	91 332	1 022 259	1 113 591
7	CHECK "trader" ATB	8 380	67 803	76 183
8	ATB "Village construction bank"	18 499	243 333	261 832
9	"Turonbank" ATB	15 783	148 771	164 554
10	CHECK "Hamkorbank" ATB	69 714	716 852	786 566
11	"Asaka" ATB	19 546	561 568	581 114
12	"Silk way" AITB	18 783	314 381	333 164
13	"Agriculture Bank Uzbekistan" AJ	1 174	13 218	14 392
14	"Trustbank" XAB	19 871	81 795	101 666
15	AT "Alokabank"	14 739	244 809	259 548
16	"KDB Bank Uzbekistan" AJ	600	31 664	32 264
17	"Turkestan" XATB	2 805	7 570	10 375
18	Iran "Soderot" subsidiary bank	128	741	869
19	"Universal bank" ATB	3 371	36 369	39 740
20	"Kapitalbank" ATB	21 519	128 297	149 816
21	"Ravnakbank" XATB	1 675	8 801	10 476
22	"Davir-Bank" XATB	17 772	49 817	67 589
23	CHECK "Invest Finance bank" ATB	16 601	212 520	229 121
24	"Asia Alliance bank" ATB	9 551	109 447	118 998
25	"Hi-Tech bank" XATB	1 337	20 261	21 598
26	"Orient finance" XATB	9 492	150 207	159 699
27	"Help Invest bank" ATB	427	2 235	2 662
28	"Uzagroexportbank" ATB	107	389	496
29	"The capital bank" AJ	511	1 796	2 307
30	"Tenge bank" ATB	56	125	181
Total	Total	691 008	9 462 450	10 153 458

Remote banking services are provided in the segment of legal entities and private entities, as well as individuals. The share of TIF National Bank, Agrobank,

People's Bank, Ipoteka-bank and Sanoatkurilishbank in the total number of Mazur system users is incomparable, and their combined share is almost 50 percent.

Table 2

Rating of mobile applications of commercial banks created for providing remote services to individuals [8]

No	Program name	Bank name	The program download those who received the number	Play Marketat price those who put the number	Average placedprice
1.	National	National Bank	100 000+	3 457	3.4
2.	Partner Mobile	Partner bank	100 000+	2 733	3.7
3.	InfinBank	Infinbank	100 000+	2 249	3.9
4.	Ipal The way Mobile	Silk The way Bank	100 000+	1 881	4.0
5.	Mortgage Bank	Mortgage bank	100 000+	1 645	4.5
6.	Agrobank Mobile New	Agrobank	100 000+	1 523	3.8
7.	Uz PSB Mobile	Industrial Construction Bank	100 000+	1 415	3.6
8.	Orange	Kapitalbank	50 000+	4 722	4.6
9.	Communication Mobile	Aloqabank	50 000+	1 126	3.9
10.	MKB Mobile	Microcredit bank	50 000+	470	3.3
11.	Asaka Mobile	Asaka Bank	50 000+	266	3.2
12.	MyAlliance	Asia Alliance Bank	10 000+	564	3.6
13.	MyTuron	Turonbank	10 000+	399	4.4
14.	OFB24	Orient Finance Bank	10 000+	397	2.6
15.	QQB Mobile	Village Construction Bank	10 000+	300	3.3
16.	People Mobile	People bank	10 000+	159	3.0
17.	TrustPay	Trustbank	10 000+	111	2.6
18.	RBK-Mobile	Ravnakbank	5 000+	115	4.5
19.	Merchant Mobile	Savdogarbank	5 000+	54	2.5

20.	DAVRBANK	Current bank	5 000+	37	3.0
21.	UNO	Hi Tech Bank	1 000+	87	3.6
22.	MultiPay KDB	KDB Bank Uzbekistan	1 000+	63	3.3
23.	Turkestan Bank	Turkestanbank	1 000+	41	3.6
24.	UniversalPay	Universalbank	1 000+	30	3.0
25.	ZiraatBank Uzbekistan	Agriculture Bank Uzbekistan	1 000+	9	3.1
26.	Help Invest Bnak Mobile	Help Invest Bank	100+	6	3.0
27.	The capital Mobile	Poytakhtbank	10+	0	0.0

When users are analyzed by separate segments, the largest share of legal entities corresponds to the contribution of the Mortgage Bank, and the share of individuals corresponds to the contribution of TIF National Bank.

As a result of research carried out by the website www.bankers.uz, a ranking of mobile applications created for providing remote services to individuals provided by commercial banks was compiled (Table 2).

It can be seen from the table that there are 7 banks with more than 100,000 downloads of mobile applications through the Play Market - InFinBank, Hamkorbank, Uzmilliybank, Agrobank, Ipoteka Bank, Silk Road Bank and OzSQB's mobile

applications. It should also be mentioned that the Asakabank mobile application is among the applications with more than 50,000 downloads.

A total of 23,900 people rated mobile applications of 27 banks available on Play Market.

The most rated mobile applications through Play Market are "Apelsin" (Kapitalbank), "Milliy" (UzMilliybank), "Hamkor Mobile" (Hamkor Bank), "InfinBank" (Infinbank) and "Ipak Yo'li Mobile". (Silk Road Bank). Among these programs, Kapitalbank's "Apelsin" application (4.6 points) has the highest rating. It is worth noting that this program has been evaluated by a total of 4722 users through the Play Market.

At this point, it should be noted that Ipoteka bank mobile applications were evaluated by 1645 users, and the average score was 4.5 points.

Without the development of digital banking, it is difficult to imagine a modern banking system today, but any technology is able to prevent and design new risks that arise as a result of their practical implementation. Considering these problems, there is a growing need to develop additional controls to ensure the safe operation of new technological solutions:

- * insufficient profitability of credit and financial organizations associated with low return on investment or profit from equity capital;

- * high expectations of consumers related to the development of remote technologies and service provision to ensure the required quality of service;

- * increased competition from companies engaged in financial technologies, which creates problems and difficulties for traditional banks that do not have the opportunity to adapt to changes not only in the field of technology, but also in financial operations, culture and other aspects of social activity;

- * due to increasing regulatory requirements, banks must spend a large part of their discretionary budgets on their compliance, as well as develop systems and processes for their development, taking into account the growing needs of customers.

In this regard, a decisive condition for overcoming these obstacles is for all participants of the financial market to manage risks, which are used not only within the framework of sectoral development, but also to ensure the competitiveness of the economy by increasing the efficiency of technologies and reducing uncertainty in the external and internal environment. It is necessary to create a qualitatively new information system.

The automated system provides better decision-making related to bank risk in granting loans, investments and securities through special procedures of processing all the data available in the system. The use of an automated system significantly improves the quality of service to bank customers, which is especially important in real competition.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result of the analysis of the prospects for the development of remote banking services in Uzbekistan, the following proposals and recommendations were developed:

1. Each commercial bank should develop its own strategic program for the development of remote banking services in commercial banks, the development of a remote customer service system. In this program, it will be necessary to develop a road map for the step-by-step transfer of all types of services to remote and online mode.

In this road map, it is necessary to mention the source of financing of the tasks, the implementation period, the department responsible for implementation, and the project launch period.

2. Currently, the types of services provided remotely by commercial banks include utility and other payments, card-to-card money transfers, online conversion, online deposit services, as well as retail lending services in some banks. and it is advisable to increase their type at the next stage. In particular, these include sending and receiving funds abroad through integration into international money transfers, including the service of virtual emission of plastic cards.

3. It is natural that the development of remote banking services creates the need to identify customers. Taking this into account, it would be appropriate to create opportunities for integration of all mobile banking services from the database of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the event of the need to identify an employee when providing customer service.

Studies have shown that in some cases there are significant deficiencies in the organizational and management models of banking organizations, and inconsistencies between the functions of employees and data processing algorithms included in automated systems are identified.

The most clearly indicated shortcomings and contradictions are manifested when non-obvious, atypical situations arise, one of the examples of which is discussed in this article.

Eliminating the identified contradictions is a necessary condition for the further development of the financial and credit sector as an independent sector in the digital economy. For this we need to introduce:

- * improvement of management in banking organizations, introduction of vertical and horizontal communication between authorized employees of different divisions of the bank;

- * development and implementation of models for processing atypical situations during the implementation of business processes;

- * integration of models of processing of atypical situations during the implementation of work processes with the current work flow systems and control of the execution of work tasks;

- * Development of secure software requirements that implement ABS functions;

- *consolidated development of ABS functionality and safety requirements by the professional community;

- *starting a new line of training for software security professionals.

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